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**AN ANALYSIS OF SURFACE AND GROWTH DIFFERENCES IN PLANTS OF
DIFFERENT STAGES USING IMAGE PROCESSING**

Faizur Rashid and Tamirat Delesa

Department of Computer Science, College of Computing and Informatics Haramaya University

ABSTRACT

Genomes are main reason for growth and surface differences in the plants. All plants grow on basis of their different surrounding like soil, water, breed of seed, and climatic session. This paper attempts to find stem growth from birth to maturity level of selected plant using image processing technique. Few reasons have been observed commonly by the researchers that some plants could not grow sufficiently as to the other plants of similar breed and age. Images were taken of different stage of bean plant and images of some other plant samples were also included for better assessment. Researchers are trying to understand through their calculative analysis by image processing emulator in MATLAB to view its reasons. Suitable comparison technique is applied to detect their period of growth. Image processing methods like Restoration, stem or leaves spots, filtering, and plant comparison have applied in MATLAB. Those effects that are not supporting to grow the plants of their similar age group are matter to calculate scientifically later in the future. The observation would help for further support in medicinal science or agricultural science of plant and Bio-chemical.

KEYWORDS

Image Processing, Surface of Plants (SOP), Differences of Stage (DoS), Segmentation.

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